

C-SCALE

D3.6 Periodical assessment of the services V3

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Deliverable Abstract

This report presents an update of the assessment of the C-SCALE services provided through the Virtual Access (VA) mechanism to the users. These include computing and storage resources. The deliverable describes the existing VA installations, their management within the project, updates the usage metrics delivered from the start of the project (January 2021) until Month 24 (December 2022) and reports on the Green Computing metrics and initiatives from the C-SCALE providers.

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
CO	Collaborative Organisation
C-SCALE	Copernicus - eoSC AnaLytics Engine
DIAS	Data and Information Access Services
EO	Earth Observation
EODC	Earth Observation Data Centre (C-SCALE provider)
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC DIH	European Open Science Cloud - Digital Innovation Hub
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GRNET	Greek Research and Technology Network (C-SCALE provider)
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HiSea	High Resolution Copernicus-Based Information Services at Sea for Ports and Aquaculture
HPC	High Performance Computing
HTC	High Throughput Computing
HTDP	High Throughput Data Processing
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
INCD-NCG	Infraestrutura Nacional de Computação Distribuída-National Computing Grid (C-SCALE provider)
OLA	Operational Level Agreement
OPEX	Operating Expense
PBS	Portable Batch System
PaaS	Platform as a Service
PUE	Power usage effectiveness
REF	Renewable energy factor
SLA	Service Level Agreement

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SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SRAM	SURF Research Access Management
STAC	SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog
TB	Terabyte
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VA	Virtual Access
VM	Virtual Machine
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

C-SCALE brings together European commercial (e.g., Copernicus DIAS) and public computing and storage providers to deliver a federated infrastructure to support Copernicus and Earth Observation (EO) use cases that deal with data- and compute-intensive workloads. The federation enables the access to a set of computing and storage resources, called *installations*, operated by the partners of the project, and deployed via a Virtual Access mechanism. Almost 20% of the total C-SCALE budget is devoted to cover the costs of these installations that the project will deliver to EOSC users as services.

This document updates the previous reports provided in Month 18 (June 2022) and in Month 14 (February 2022) – originally planned in Month 12 (December 2021) – on the usage of Virtual Access for C-SCALE providers.

C-SCALE installations now support 16 different use cases: six of them are internal to the project, while the other 10 come from the C-SCALE Open Call and the EOSC DIH Expression of Interest for Business Pilots. The installations also provide resources for supporting the activities related to the evaluation testbed for C-SCALE services, the development of the project’s Metadata Query Service as well as the maintenance of the project’s website. All these use cases are in different stages of development, from testing and piloting to production, so the consumption of VA varies from one use case to another. The overall consumption of VA in the project has increased over the last period as the number of use cases and their maturity have increased. It’s expected that the VA usage will keep increasing over the last project’s period.

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1 Introduction

This deliverable provides the third assessment of the C-SCALE services based on the Virtual Access (VA) installations of the project, which provide the computing and storage resources that power the C-SCALE services that will be made available through EOSC. Deliverable D3.4 introduced the VA installations and the initial usage delivered until November 2021, and an update of the usage collected until the end of Month 18 (June 2022) was provided in Deliverable D3.5. In this document we report on the status of the VA usage for the providers of C-SCALE until December 2022 (M24). D3.7 will report on the usage until at the end of the project (June 2023). After the initial phase, where only the applications from the project's use cases were accessing and consuming resources from the C-SCALE providers, in this updated version we report the newly accepted use cases from the Open Call¹ and their planned consumption of resources.

There have not been any changes in the 23 installations from the C-SCALE providers since the start of the project, but a future amendment will fix some calculation errors in the VA installation description forms. This amendment is under preparation and will be officialised before the next deliverable D3.7. The current installations are described in more detail in D3.4 and summarised in Table 1 below.

Table 1. C-SCALE Installations per provider and category

Provider	VA installation	Category	Mode of access	Unit of access
EODC	EODC EO storage	Storage	Secure Shell (ssh)	TB/year
	EODC EO Cloud	Cloud IaaS	OpenStack ² APIs	CPU/year
	EODC HPC	HPC/HTC	ssh	CPU/hour
CESNET	MetaCentrumCloud - CPU	Cloud IaaS	OpenStack API/GUI + PBS ³	CPU core/month
INFN	INFN Bari Storage	Storage	OpenStack APIs	TB/month
	INFN Bari CPU	Cloud IaaS	OpenStack APIs	CPU core/month
SURF	SURFsara dCache Front end storage	Storage	ssh	TiByte*Year
	SURFsara Spider (HTDP) Storage	Storage	ssh	TB*Year

¹ C-SCALE Open Call <https://c-scale.eu/call-for-use-cases>. See also D5.2 D5.2 Criteria for choosing candidates for the Early Adopter Programme <https://zenodo.org/record/4749475>

² OpenStack is an Open Source Cloud Software, see <https://www.openstack.org/>

³ Portable Batch System, a batch scheduling system, see <https://www.openpbs.org/>

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	SURFsara Data Processing Compute	HPC/HTC	ssh	CPU*Hour
	SURFsara MS4 Storage	Storage	ssh	TB*Year
	SURFsara MS4 SSD Storage	Storage	ssh	TB*Month
	SURFsara MS4 Compute	Cloud IaaS	ssh	CPU*Hour
VITO	VITO CVB (Storage)	Storage	via Notebooks, VMs, openEO ⁴ API	TB/Month
	VITO CVB (CPU)	Cloud IaaS	SSH & openEO API	CPU/hour
GRNET	GRNET KNS - Storage Cloud	Storage	OpenStack APIs	TB*Hour
	GRNET KNS - Cloud	Cloud IaaS	OpenStack APIs	Core*Hour
	GRNET ARIS - Storage HPC	Storage	ssh	TB*Hour
	GRNET ARIS - CPU HPC	HPC/HTC	ssh	Core*Hour
CloudFerro	CREODIAS - Storage	Storage	OpenStack APIs	TB/month
	CREODIAS - Compute	Cloud IaaS	OpenStack APIs	vCore/hour
	CREODIAS - GPU	Cloud IaaS	OpenStack APIs	VMGPU/hour
INCD	INCD Lisbon (NCG) (Storage)	Storage	OpenStack APIs	TB*month
	INCD Lisbon (NCG) (Compute)	Cloud IaaS	OpenStack APIs	CPU*month

Currently, these installations support use cases from WP4 and those use cases from the Open Call that are ready to deploy their workflows in the infrastructure.

⁴ openEO: an open API to connect to Earth observation cloud back-ends, see <https://openeo.org/>

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2 Virtual Access Metrics

Each installation of C-SCALE defines a set of metrics to report VA usage to the project, with a clear description of the metrics and how the measurement is done by the provider. These metrics are reported on a 3-monthly basis to the internal project workspace (Confluence) by the providers.

C-SCALE implements an SLA (Service Level Agreement)/OLA (Operational Level Agreement) framework that tracks, for all use cases, the agreed number of resources and the conditions to access them. Currently, there are agreements in place for all the active use cases within C-SCALE: six use cases from WP4 and 10 use cases from the Open Call and EOSC DIH. Additionally, two new support use cases are also covered under these agreements: the MQS and C-SCALE website Hosting, that captures the VA usage for hosting the Metadata Query Service delivered by WP2 and the C-SCALE website, and the C-SCALE Evaluation Testbed, which provides an easy access to C-SCALE resources for evaluation and training without the need of submission of a full request via the Open Call. These agreements are summarised in Table 2. Further agreements for the newly selected Open Call use cases are under negotiation and hence will be reported in subsequent deliverable D3.7.

Table 2. C-SCALE VA Agreements

Use Case	Type	Providers	Start date	End date
Aquamonitor	Project	INCD, INFN	2021-06-01	2023-06-30
RETURN	Project	SURF	2021-07-01	2023-06-30
LSDA	Project	SURF	2021-07-01	2023-06-30
HiSea	Project	GRNET	2021-07-01	2023-06-30
Wetland Water Stresses	Project	EODC, CloudFerro	2021-11-01	2023-06-30
WaterWatch	Project	CESNET, VITO	2022-02-01	2023-06-30
SAR on the fly	Open Call	CloudFerro	2022-04-25	2023-06-30
SPOTLIGHT	Open Call	EODC	2022-07-01	2023-06-30
TWC-SCUP	Open Call	EODC	2022-09-01	2023-06-30
Energie.Family	Open Call	EODC	2022-11-30	2023-06-30
UDOS	Open Call	EODC	2022-10-19	2023-06-30
KappaMask	Open Call	CloudFerro	2022-12-08	2023-06-30
Grapevine	Open Call	CloudFerro	2022-12-13	2023-06-30
GLTFCA	Open Call	INCD	2022-12-08	2023-06-30
In SAR Cubes	Open Call	CESNET	2022-09-01	2023-06-30
Coastmonitor	Open Call	INFN	2022-11-01	2023-06-30

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MQS and C-SCALE Website Hosting	Support	EODC	2021-01-20	2023-06-30
C-SCALE Evaluation testbed	Support	CESNET	2022-09-09	2023-06-30

The information in the agreements and the usage metrics from providers are used as input for the project's capacity management team formed by members of the *Operations of the Virtual Access installation* task (T3.4) and *Provider onboarding support and the VA coordination* task (T5.1). The team keeps track of the usage trends and reacts accordingly and plans the capacity allocation for the use cases to be supported.

Table 3 shows the cumulative metric values from the start of the project until M11 (as reported in D3.4), until the end of M18 (June 2022), and until M24 (December 2022) which is the last metrics collection before the writing of this deliverable. The last deliverables covering the assessment of the services (D3.7) will present the updated values for the metrics. As installations were not available before C-SCALE to EOSC users, the baseline value for all installations is 0. Table 3 contains fixes detected in the metrics reported for GRNET and INCD for M01-M18 included in D3.5.

As in D3.5, metrics related to number of users or number of use cases in Table 3 have been homogenized to show the number of use cases supported by each installation and, whenever available, also the number of individual users belonging to the supported use cases. This facilitates the comparison of the uptake of providers as the number of individual users varies depending on the usage model of each use case: from use cases where a single to few expert users are in charge of the deployment of services that final researchers will access, to use cases where each individual user interacts with the installations directly (e.g., by submitting jobs to a HPC system).

Table 3. VA Usage

VA Installation	Metric type	Description	Base line	M01 - M11	M01-M18	M01-M24
EODC EO storage	Number of users	Number of user accounts	0	0	1 use case	5 use cases
	Usage	Allocated TB/year	0	0	0.42 TB*year	16.80 TB/year
	Number of countries reached	Number of countries from the user accounts	0	0	1	4
	Names of countries reached	Names of countries from the user accounts	-	-	Austria	Austria Germany Greece France

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EODC EO Cloud	Number of users	Number of user accounts	0	1	1 use case	5 use cases
	Usage	Time of VM usage	0	1.33 CPU/Year	10.64 CPU/Year	77.97 CPU/year
	Number of countries reached	Number of countries from the user accounts	0	1	1	2
	Names of countries reached	Names of countries from the user accounts	0	Austria	Austria	Austria Germany
EODC HPC	Number of users	Number of user accounts	0	0	0	0
	Usage	CPU hours	0	0	0	0
	Number of countries reached	Number of countries from the user accounts	0	0	0	0
	Names of countries reached	Names of countries from the user accounts	-	-	-	-
MetaCentrumCloud - CPU	Number of users	Number of user consuming CPU resources	0	0	1 use case (1 user)	3 (16 users)
	Usage	CPU core months consumed (with typically 4GB of RAM per core)	0	0	10 CPU core/month	524 CPU core/month
	Number of countries reached	Number of countries from the user accounts	0	0	1	3
	Names of countries reached	Names of countries from	-	-	Czechia	Czechia, United

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		the user accounts				Kingdom, Netherlands
INFN Bari Storage	Number of user communities	Communities supported by the installation	0	0	0	2 use cases
	Usage	TB used / month	0	0	0	0.78 TB month
INFN Bari CPU	Number of user communities	Communities supported by the installation	0	0	0	2 use cases
	Usage	CPU hours	0	0	0	55.61 CPU month
SURFsara dCache Front end storage	Number of users	Number of registered C-SCALE users	0	0	0	0
	Usage	Number of TB per year consumed by C-SCALE users	0	0	0	0
	Satisfaction	Degree of C-SCALE user satisfaction	0	-	-	-
SURFsara Spider (HTDP) Storage	Number of users	Number of registered C-SCALE users	0	14	2 use cases (18 users)	2 use cases (29 users)
	Usage	Number of TB per year consumed by C-SCALE users	0	19.15 TB*Year	41.79 TB*year	64.46 TB*Year
	Satisfaction ⁵	Degree of C-SCALE user satisfaction	0	4	5	5
SURFsara Data Processing Compute	Number of users	Number of registered C-SCALE users	0	14	2 use cases (18 users)	2 use cases (29 users)

⁵ Measures customer satisfaction based on a feedback survey that grades services from 1-5 (being very dissatisfied and 5 being very satisfied)

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	Usage	Wall time CPU core hours consumed by C-SCALE users	0	143,599 CPU*hours	247,962 CPU*hours	370,328 CPU*hours
	Satisfaction	Degree of C-SCALE user satisfaction	0	4	4	4
SURFsara MS4 Storage	Number of users	Number of registered C-SCALE users	0	0	0	0
	Usage	Number of TB per year consumed by C-SCALE users	0	0	0	0
	Satisfaction	Degree of C-SCALE user satisfaction	0	-	-	-
SURFsara MS4 SSD Storage	Number of users	Number of registered C-SCALE users	0	0	0	0
	Usage	Number of TB per year consumed by C-SCALE users	0	0	0	0
	Satisfaction	Degree of C-SCALE user satisfaction	0	-	-	-
SURFsara MS4 Compute	Number of users	Number of registered C-SCALE users	0	0	0	0
	Usage	Wall time CPU core hours consumed by C-SCALE users	0	0	0	0
	Satisfaction	Degree of C-SCALE user satisfaction	0	-	-	-
VITO CVB (Storage)	Number of users	User that created an account and has actively	0	0	0	0

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		logged into a VM or used an API service				
	Usage	Time in months for VM usage and in hours for Hadoop usage	0	0	0	0
	Number of countries reached	Number of countries reached using our datawarehousing system	0	0	0	0
	Names of the countries reached	Names of countries from the user accounts	-	-	-	-
VITO CVB (CPU)	Number of users	User that logged in to openEO	0	0	1 use case (5 users)	2 use cases (7 users)
	Usage	Time in months for VM usage and in hours for Hadoop usage	0	0	16,660 CPU Hours	276,349 CPU Hours
VITO CVB (CPU)	Number of countries reached	Number of countries reached using our datawarehousing system	0	0	0	1
	Names of the countries reached	Names of countries from the user accounts	-	-	-	The Netherlands
GRNET KNS - Storage Cloud	Number of users	Number of users accessing the service	0	11	1 use case (11 users)	1 use case (11 users)

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	Usage	Total number of TB Hours for the duration of the project	0	363.40 TB*Hours	894.24 TB*Hours	1,538.98 TB*Hours
GRNET KNS - Cloud	Number of users	Number of users accessing the service	0	11	1 use case (11 users)	1 use case (11 users)
	Usage	Total number of virtual CPU hours with 2 GB of RAM consumed for the duration of the project	0	93,137.71 Core*Hours	217,138.03 Core*Hours	353,284.07 Core*Hours
GRNET ARIS - Storage HPC	Number of users	Number of users accessing the service	0	5	1 use case (5 users)	1 use case (5 users)
	Usage	Total number of TB hours for the duration of the project	0	1.36 TB*Hours	131.62 TB*Hours	293.03 TB*Hours
GRNET ARIS - CPU HPC	Number of users	Number of users accessing the service	0	5	1 use case (5 users)	1 use case (5 users)
	Usage	Total number of CPU core hours with 2 GB of RAM consumed for the duration of the project	0	170 Core*Hours	326 Core*Hours	326 Core*Hours
CREODIAS - Storage	Number of users	Users that create an account and logged into OpenStack dashboard or used API services	0	0	2 use cases (2 users)	5 use cases (7 users)

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	Usage	Number of credits in pay-per-use model	0	0	20 TB*Month	58 TB*Month
CREODIAS - Compute	Number of users	Users that create an account and logged into OpenStack dashboard or used API services	0	0	2 use cases (2 users)	5 use cases (7 users)
	usage	Number of credits in pay-per-use model	0	0	7,866.76 vCPU*hours	81,800.39 vCPU*hours
CREODIAS - GPU	Number of users	Users that create an account and logged into OpenStack dashboard or used API services	0	0	2 use cases (2 users)	5 use cases (7 users)
	Usage	Number of credits in pay-per-use model	0	0	407.27 VMGPU*hours	617,73 VMGPU*hours
INCD Lisbon (NCG) (Storage)	Number of users	Total number of new users	0	4	1 use case (4 users)	2 use case (5 users)
	Usage	Total storage (unit TB*month) allocated to the project	0	62.015	167 TB*month	201 TB*month
	Number of countries reached	Total number of new countries	0	1	1	2
	Names of the countries reached	Names of countries from the user accounts	-	The Netherlands	The Netherlands	The Netherlands Zambia

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INCD Lisbon (NCG) (Compute)	Number of users	Total number of new users	0	4	1 use case (4 users)	2 use case (5 users)
	Usage	Total number of virtual VCPU*month with 2 GB of RAM consumed for the duration of the project	-	431.71 CPU*month	1279.71 CPU*month	2351.01 CPU*month
	Number of countries reached	Total number of new countries	0	1	1	1
	Names of the countries reached	Names of countries from the user accounts	-	The Netherlands	The Netherlands	The Netherlands Zambia

It is noted that the VA usage of SURF and GRNET, as reported in Table 3, refer to the period from January 2021 (M1) until the end of November 2022 (M23).

Table 4 shows the consumption in percent of the available units for all the installations. As planned in the project, the VA usage during the initial months of the project has been mostly related to test activities to make the new federation access channels fully operational and to integrate the existing use cases.

Table 4. VA Consumption

Provider	VA installation	Available units	Consumed M1 - M24
EODC	EODC EO storage	150 TB/year	11.2%
	EODC EO Cloud	620 CPU/year	12.58%
	EODC HPC	600,000 CPU/hour	0.00%
CESNET	MetaCentrumCloud - CPU	2,850 CPU core/month	18%
INFN	INFN Bari Storage	1,500 TB/month	0.05%
	INFN Bari CPU	3,840CPU core/month	1.45%
SURF	SURFsara dCache Front end storage	154 TiByte*Year	0.00%
	SURFsara Spider (HTDP) Storage	160 TB*Year	40.29%

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	SURFsara Data Processing Compute	1,500,000 CPU*Hour	24.69%
	SURFsara MS4 Storage	10 TB*Year	0.00%
	SURFsara MS4 SSD Storage	96 TB*Month	0.00%
	SURFsara MS4 Compute	147,600 CPU*Hour	0.00%
VITO	VITO CVB (Storage)	266 TB/Month	0.00%
	VITO CVB (CPU)	292,00 ⁶ CPU/hour	94.6%
GRNET	GRNET KNS - Storage Cloud	250,000 TB*Hour	0.62%
	GRNET KNS - Cloud	1,650,000 Core*Hour	21.41%
	GRNET ARIS - Storage HPC	219000 TB*Hour	0.13%
	GRNET ARIS - CPU HPC	1,000,000 Core*Hour	0.03%
CloudFerro	CREODIAS - Storage	2,762 TB/month	2.10%
	CREODIAS - Compute	1,500,000 vCore/hour	5.45%
	CREODIAS - GPU	6,000 VMGPU/hour	10.28%
INCD	INCD Lisbon (NCG) (Storage)	450 TB*month	49.63%
	INCD Lisbon (NCG) (Compute)	4500 CPU*month	52.24%

EODC is currently supporting five different use cases, from Austria and Germany, and has significantly increased their Virtual Access resource provision since the last reporting (in M18). More specifically, EODC continues to provide VA resources to the Wetland Water Stresses use case, which is implemented by TU Wien, based in Austria, running on EODC EO Cloud since November 2021, and using EODC EO Storage since February 2022. In July 2022, the use case SPOTLIGHT, from the Paris Lodron University Salzburg, Austria, was onboarded and started using the EODC EO Storage installation. The SPOTLIGHT project aims to provide on-demand semantically enriched satellite imagery datacubes on request. The project was further expanded in September and October and EODC provided further resources from their EODC EO Cloud installation. TWC-SCUP (Scaling Up of Tama WaldCursor), a use case from TAMA Group, Germany, was onboarded in September 2022 through the EOSC DIH with a ready-to-use service for forestry. The plan of this project is to scale up the TAMA Forest app to a larger Area of Interest, and for that they have been using both the EODC EO Storage and Cloud installations. Another use case onboarded in September 2022 to the EODC EO Storage and EO Cloud through the EOSC DIH was the Urban Dynamics Observation Service (UDOS), from ubicube, based in Austria, focusing on providing satellite information to the real estate sector.

⁶ The original figure in VITO's installation had an error in the calculation. An amendment is currently under preparation to fix the errors. This report shows the corrected figures already.

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The latest use case onboarded was NC4EC, from Energie.Family, based in Germany, and it focused on solar nowcasting for energy communities using meteorological satellite data to inform energy communities about their current solar power potential. All mentioned use cases will continue consuming VA resources until the end of the project in June 2023. In addition, EODC continues to provide Sentinel-1 pre-processed data for the RETURN use case and is expecting to host the High-Resolution Land Surface Drought Analysis (LSDA) use case HPC scale up on the HPC infrastructure. Finally, EODC is hosting the C-SCALE website and the Metadata Query Service (MQS) on their EODC EO Cloud installation.

CESNET has been supporting three separate use cases, or modes of usage of the compute resources. Firstly, the WaterWatch use case, whose initial stages (until M18) consisted mostly of preparatory work but from there onwards the resources have been used for data discovery and analysis. Secondly CESNET has been supporting the C-SCALE Evaluation Virtual Organisation (VO), which is a low-threshold entry VO for users wishing to evaluate C-SCALE's interactive or cloud environments. Especially between M18 and M24 resources allocated to this VO have been used for hands-on training, and evaluation of the use of Jupyter Notebooks in C-SCALE. Thirdly there was the In-SAR-Cubes use case, which commenced operation in fall 2022 and has been using allocated cloud resources for Sentinel-1 interferometry analysis.

INFN has started the support to the Aquamonitor and Coastmonitor communities to access INFN resources focusing on leveraging the automation and orchestration capabilities of the INDIGO PaaS Orchestrator. This will help to easily deploy the use case over heterogeneous Cloud infrastructures, both from EOSC providers like C-SCALE and EGI, or public providers like AWS, Azure, etc, without extra human effort and without the need to gain IT know-how on the underneath cloud solution. So far, the support has consisted in the setup of the PaaS Orchestrator recipes to deploy the openEO platform needed to support the use cases. The VA consumption of INFN is associated to this initial support activity.

SURF has been supporting two use cases (i) *REcovery of Tropical Forest Using Radar seNtinel time series* (RETURN) and (ii) *High Resolution Land Surface Drought Analysis* (LSDA) use cases in the period M1-24. Initially, the RETURN use case focused on Sentinel-2 (S2) and Landsat imaging data. A pipeline creating analysis ready data cubes has been fully deployed on the SURF data processing (HTC) infrastructure. However, due to changes in personnel, this use case has shifted its focus from S-2 to Sentinel-1 (S-1) radar data. As previously reported, this required significant human support by SURF. Since the previous report, SURF provided additional support to RETURN in particular by adding and re-syncing new data from EODC and providing test and scale-up scripts. The use case is currently checking their custom data analysis pipelines with support from EODC and SURF. Once completed, the use case can immediately scale from a single tile to full dataset covering the entire amazon basin area of interest. For the LSDA case SURF has continued to provide support and engaged in user support meeting. During this period less human support from SURF was needed as the LSDA workflow has been running smoothly on the SURF provided infrastructure. Currently plans are being made to scale this case up in early 2023 at SURF and to also re-deploy it on resources provided by EODC at TUW. Several SURF VA installations haven't delivered any VA resources as the current use cases do not match the functionality delivered by these installations.

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VITO has supported the use of openEO in their installations for the WaterWatch and Aquamonitor use cases. Besides the provisioning of resources, VITO has provided extensive support for porting the use cases to the openEO framework ensuring the applications can run on the C-SCALE providers, as well as supporting the providers in configuring the openEO system on their infrastructures. In the frame of both WaterWatch and Aquamonitor, a Kubernetes cluster on CreoDIAS, with access to multiple large EO data archives (Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2) was used to test scalability and data access performance, allowing to work concurrently while other providers were still working on provisioning of EO-data and configuring the openEO system on Kubernetes. For functional, small-scale, testing of both use cases the openEO instance in Terrascope has been used. It is expected that this allows for a smooth transition to INFN, INCD and CESNET once they have the openEO system running with access to the EO data required by the use case.

GRNET has been actively supporting – in terms of resources and technical support – the HiSea use case, for the period M01-M24. Two major facilities are provided: Cloud and HPC, both delivering CPU and storage resources. On the cloud, one VM with 16 cores is used for the pre- and post-processing in the use case and a second VM is deployed as an NFS-Server with an additional 300 TB storage for data caching. Additionally, a STAC endpoint is deployed and registered in the GOCDDB. Moreover, in the HPC infrastructure, HiSea users have already access to run jobs on the “fat nodes” partition of the HPC infrastructure⁷ (40 cores per node). The VA consumption in this HPC infrastructure is attributable to the setup and testing of the system, such as calculating the scalability and the performance efficiency of the production code using Singularity⁸ containers. Previously, the HiSea users were focusing on the pre/post-processing phases happening in the Cloud domain. Currently, they are developing the HPC-related flow. Finally, a new use case is arriving at the beginning of the next year.

During M01-M24, CloudFerro became the resource provider of five projects so far: *Wetland Water Stress*, *SAR on the fly*, *HiSea*, *KappaMask* and *Grapevine*. CloudFerro provides GPU for the needs of SAR on the Fly and *Wetland Water Stress* projects, which helps to get results faster for their needs. HiSea project started in August 2022 and is running only on CPU currently. Two newest projects KappaMask and Grapevine are using CloudFerro compute infrastructure as well. Additionally, a new kind of installation for delivering remote data access using S3 interface is currently under discussion and piloting. This new installation will support downloading data to other providers of the federation to enable the distributed processing of data.

INCD has deployed a Kubernetes cluster on top of an OpenStack cluster to support C-SCALE use cases. The Kubernetes cluster is composed of 10 nodes with 16 cores and 32 GB of RAM each where openEO is deployed. The first approach was to create a single volume of 12TB for the storage of data for the Aquamonitor use case, but it has been changed to a S3 bucket that is mounted on every single compute node, allowing for the sharing of data both within the cluster and the outside world. A local STAC server has been deployed to download satellite imagery products directly to a S3 Bucket

⁷ See technical description of nodes at <https://doc.aris.grnet.gr/system/hardware/#fat-nodes>

⁸ <https://sylabs.io/singularity>

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Which is then used by openEO. A python script was developed to register the metadata of the downloaded products in the user STAC catalogue available at CESNET, in this way all the data that is stored in our S3 bucket can be discovered on the catalogue at CESNET. The aforementioned script had a bug and that was solved, so the registration of the metadata had to be done again. We have also discovered some bugs on Vito's docker images and helped with the debug of those issues. A jupyter notebook was used to test out our endpoint which led to the discovery of the previously mentioned bugs. A zookeeper service was deployed on our cluster which led to the discovery of some other issues regarding the k8s cinder plugin. Those issues were all solved, and we are currently still working with VITO to debug their docker images. The deployment of the cluster was done using kubespray, following the GitOPS approach, as well as all the above-mentioned services, that were deployed using GitLab pipelines. This allowed us to deploy and redeploy any of the services with minimal "human intervention".

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3 Green Computing

C-SCALE WP3’s manages the Tier-1 aspects of Green Computing of the project, defined as follows:

Tier 1: Analysis of the “Direct environmental OPEX” of C-SCALE by tracking the energy consumption of the computing centres. Monitoring of the KPIs (PUE and REF) defined in the EN-50600-4⁹ across as many of the computing centres as possible and the use of additional indicators (such as reuse of the heat of the computing centre or carbon intensity of the electricity supply) where available.

Table 5 reports the available metrics for the providers for the green computing aspects wherever these are available. These were already reported in D3.5 and are repeated here for the sake of completion.

Table 5. Green Computing aspects of the providers

Provider	Metrics	Comments
EODC	PUE: 1.22 ¹⁰ REF: 0.67 ¹¹	<p>Efficiency and environmentally responsible computing are a strong theme at EODC.</p> <p>To support this, the following measures are considered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power supplies for storage and compute systems are either 80 Plus Platinum rated, or equivalent, following compliance with Commission Regulation (EU) 2019/424 (Directive 2009/125/EC). • The primary datacentre makes use of a free cooling setup completed in 2019. This is further enhanced with turbo technology, whereby exhaust airflow is used to further improve efficiency. <p>The latest iteration of EODC HPC, based on the VSC-5 ranks at 90 in the Green 500 – An international ranking of supercomputer power efficiently – and offers 4.48 Gflops/Watts¹²</p>
CESNET	PUE: 1.6	CESNET actively monitors energy consumption of production clusters.

⁹ CENELEC EN 50600-4-1:2016 Information technology - Data centre facilities and infrastructures - Part 4-1: Overview of and general requirements for key performance indicators
https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=CENELEC:110:::FSP_PROJECT,FSP_ORG_ID:60776,1258297&cs=1EE9B4ACAAAF98EFCDA91E2949FBE95F1E

¹⁰ PUE calculation excluded energy efficiency of the IT load, its utilisation or productivity.

¹¹ The REF calculation refers to the entire building where the datacentre is hosted

¹² See <https://www.top500.org/lists/green500/2022/06/>

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INFN	n/a	INFN is actively studying measures to implement a green approach on running the ReCaS-Bari Data Centre. INFN is planning the implementation of a direct free cooling solution inside the data centre. In the short term INFN is deeply investing time in studying the optimization on cooling systems depending on the status of usage of the IT resources.
SURF	PUE: 1.22 REF: 1	SURF tracks energy consumption of the data centres hosting C-SCALE workloads and is actively working on tracking the carbon footprint of the infrastructure. SURF is not under direct control of the PUE and REF metrics of the data centres as SURF acts as a tenant for those.
VITO	n/a	VITO's computing resource supplier has Class 3 Compliant design with EN 50600. Moreover, with continuous performance improvements through OpenEO, VITO is aiming to reduce the need for computing resources for EO data processing.
GRNET	PUE: 1.6	GRNET is actively working on tracking the carbon footprint of the infrastructure, while it measures the energy consumption of the data centres that deliver all the workloads.
CloudFerro	PUE: 1.65	CloudFerro's data centre for provisioning C-Scale resources has Class 3 Compliant design with EN 50600.
INCD	PUE: 1.45	Since the early start of the INCD, reducing the carbon footprint of the infrastructure is one of the major goals. To accomplish this, over the last years, a series of investments and procedures have been implemented on the operational data centre. The measures were: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Installation of new racks and replacement of the old supply circuits with new Power Distribution Units (PDU), with real-time consumption measures. The new PDU's effectively increase the efficiency of data centre power usage. ● Inclusion in public tendering specifications, CPU power consumption (SPEC per watt) and power supplies with 80 Plus Titanium certification. ● Implementation of free-cooling, requiring a re-design of the cooling system and chillers replacements by new

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		units optimized to the climate conditions (subtropical in the case of Lisbon, Portugal).
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4 Conclusions

All C-SCALE Virtual Access providers are now engaged with use cases of the project. The conditions and resources available for each use case are captured on Virtual Access Agreements documents, ensuring customers and providers have clear expectations on the delivered service and support the capacity planning of the project.

Until M12 the usage reported was mostly due to testing integration of the providers, in the period M12-M18 the infrastructure has started to be actively used by all the use cases. Now in M24, the infrastructure has started to support a wider number of use cases and hence the consumption has increased at several providers. Figure 1 shows the percentage of VA consumed per installation type (storage and processing). CPU usage has significantly increased in the last period and as more use cases are onboarded this trend is expected to continue. Storage usage increased also over the last period, but it's still overall low.

Figure 1. VA Consumption per installation type

The lack of VA consumption was identified early in the project as one of possible outcomes of two project risks:

- “Lacking features for supporting use cases in WP4”. Use cases from the project are developed in parallel with the project services, thus the consumption from these was expected to be low in the early phases of the project. A close collaboration with WP4 helped to identify the most relevant features to focus WP3 developments on, but this has required a long-iterative process to provide the required functionality that is still in progress. WP4 use cases have also taken longer to develop than expected and this has delayed the scaling-out phase that should consume large amount of VA resources.
- “Not enough use cases are identified through the Early Adopter Programme”. Although the number of use cases has been growing over the last months, thanks to the services of the

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project now being ready to accommodate them, the consumption of VA from these use cases has not yet reached a level that allows for consumption of the VA resources up to the expected targets.

A new risk will be registered in the project to tackle specifically the low VA consumption in the project so far. As a mitigation plan for this risk, a detailed plan to consume the rest of the VA will be drafted for the last period of the project. The plan will start from a projection of the consumption until the end of the project, considering the maturity of the existing use cases and the new ones in the pipeline. With that information, the project may propose shifting VA units from underused installations to those more requested to better serve the users. In order to further promote C-SCALE, a set of services has been defined and described and are available from C-SCALE website¹³. Those services are aimed to provide the necessary platforms to foster the usage of the installations and services put in place by the partners. Those are being worked as Key Exploitable Results of the project part of WP5. Specifically: the Federated Earth System Simulation and Data Processing Platform (FedEarthData), the Metadata Query Service (MQS), the openEO Platform and the Workflow Solutions. In addition, C-SCALE is working on the on-boarding of those new services in EOSC. Therefore, once onboarded, access to the C-SCALE installations will also be feasible via the EOSC portal, potentially increasing the number of use cases reaching the C-SCALE providers.

¹³ <https://c-scale.eu/services/>

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